

Relationship of cross-linguistics with other fields

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Annotation

This article highlights the relationship, similarities and differences between hybrid linguistics and other disciplines. these aspects will be covered in detail in the following main sections

Keywords: Cross- linguistics, languages, differences, psychology, history, psysics

Аннотация

В данной статье освещаются взаимосвязи, сходства и различия между гибридной лингвистикой и другими дисциплинами. эти аспекты будут подробно рассмотрены в следующих основных разделах.

Ключевые слова: Кросслингвистика, языки, различия, психология, история, физика.

Crosslinguistic influence (CLI) refers to the different ways in which one language can affect another within an individual speaker. It typically involves two languages that can affect one another in a bilingual speaker. There are many subcategories of linguist, who focus on different aspects of language or on the ways that people interact with it. Some are interested in analysing the structure of languages themselves, and for these linguists a central part of their work is to build a comprehensive grammar of a language/dialect. However it's important to note that this task is one of description, not prescription. It is not a style guide, and it doesn't contain notions of what is "correct" or "incorrect", rather just recording all that is observed during a systematic survey process designed to learn the mechanics of that language.

A linguist working in this area will categorise the subject language according to accepted theoretical frameworks, employing universal notation wherever possible. In this way, the grammars of different languages can be directly compared for structural similarities and differences. And it turns out that the languages of the world have A LOT in common, even those languages with no attestable common ancestor and the languages of people who, until very recently, had no contact with the outside world. All languages have words for the basic concepts of human existence (mother, good, tree, walk, big, happy) and all languages have verbs and nouns, in some form or another.They also have certain fundamental differences. Whole many European

languages have two or three grammatical genders, some African languages have far more, and many languages of the world have none at all. English has a standard word order of subject-verb-object, whereas Japanese is S-O-V. Some languages have intricate conjugation and declension rules so that a single word conveys a wealth of information; others like Chinese have basically zero morphology and rely on word order and context to convey the relationship between the words spoken. Languages describe colours differently - a certain reddish orange might fall under the umbrella term "red" for some people, "orange" for others, and maybe even "yellow" for a few. Most languages describe direction with respect to an individual's point of view, acknowledging that your "left" is not necessarily my "left"; a minority use cardinal directions so in those languages you would be told to "turn north at the corner" and you'd instinctively know how to do that. All these similarities and differences lead to deeper questions about our perception and understanding of the world. There are not a lot of hard and fast answers, but the philosophical questions are intellectually stimulating in and of themselves. All this is made possible by the compilation of standardised grammars

psychology = psycholinguistics! Main areas of research are language perception and language production, from understanding sound systems to the mistakes people make to how fast people can and do use language. Another big field is child development, a massive part of which is first language acquisition; second language acquisition is an almost-equally large field. Related to language acquisition is bilingualism, and the cognitive effects of knowing and/or acquiring more than one language, as well as the mechanisms of bilingual acquisition.

history = historical linguistics! Language change and evolution are the name of the game: how much has a language/languages changed, and in what ways. Tracing linguistic changes back hundreds and thousands of years help historians track the movements of peoples all over the world, providing new insight as to who was where at what time doing what things, as well as advance our knowledge of which languages are descended from the same proto-language.

forensic science = forensic linguistics! This is where the law and linguistics meet. Forensic linguists do things like authorial identification of sensitive documents (ransom notes, suicide letters, threatening calls, etc.), judging the truthfulness of eyewitness testimonies, analyzing potentially violent discourse like abuse and bullying, and so on. Very important in understanding the judicial process and uncovering things like bias, like whether a judge is directing courtroom discourse towards a particular

outcome, whether a policeman's interrogation techniques are within legal confines, or whether a particular piece of written legislation marginalizes specific communities.

physics = phonetics! What? Physics? How?! Well sounds, of course! Phoneticians study the sounds in language, how they are produced and perceived by humans (see: psychology). But unlike phonologists, they focus on the physical properties of sounds: the lengths and frequencies of sound waves of all the different sounds in human languages, the use of articulators in our mouths (mainly lips, teeth and tongue), air flow through the oral and nasal cavities, and how those properties may change according to the linguistic environment.

Overproduction refers to an L2 learner producing certain structures within the L2 with a higher frequency than native speakers of that language. In a study by Schachter and Rutherford (1979), they found that Chinese and Japanese speakers who wrote English sentences overproduced certain types of cleft constructions:

'It is very unfortunate that...'

and sentences that contained There are/There is which suggests an influence of the topic marking function in their L1 appearing in their L2 English sentences. French learners have been shown to over-rely on presentational structures when introducing new referents into discourse, in their L2 Italian and English. This phenomenon has been observed even in the case of a target language where the presentational structure does not involve a relative pronoun, as Mandarin Chinese.

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